

A Road Map to Automatic Abnormal Activity Detection In Real Time Video Surveillance Using Machine And Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

Anomaly detection and crime recognition are now inevitable research matters in the deep learning and artificial intelligence age, especially in surveillance, security, and intelligent systems. This survey paper presents detailed overview of recent progress in these areas by classifying previous work into four categories Such as Crime Detection and Anomaly Detection in Surveillance, where the subject of deep learning models for crime detection and suspicious activity identification in surveillance videos is addressed, and Anomaly Detection in Video and Time-Series Data, where supervised and unsupervised machine learning methods are presented to identify anomalies in video streams and time-series data, Object and Human Activity Recognition in Smart Systems, where pedestrian detection, small object recognition, and human action classification using deep learning models are addressed.The paper critically examines a few machine learning architectures, including hybrid deep learning architectures, CNN-RNN models, 3D ConvNets, and determines their strengths, weaknesses, and implications in the real world. We also give a survey of the recent advances, challenges, and directions for future research in intelligent

surveillance systems, anomaly detection, and crime detection. Being a valuable guide to researchers and practitioners intending to enhance security, automation, and real-time anomaly detection in various contexts, this survey is a must-read. This survey was considered parameters such as Accuracy,F1-Score, Recall, Robustness, Precision for finding results.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Crime Detection, Anomaly Detection , Surveillance Security,CNN-RNN,Human-Activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The progression and path to intelligent surveillance and security systems is unavoidable in today technology driven world. High crime rates, public safety threats, and their accumulation of AI, use of deep learning algorithms is an understandable and justifiable push towards the strong capability of into intelligent surveillance, security systems.

Anomaly detection and criminal detection in to powered cameras and monitoring public safeties, which prevent crime, and determine odd behavior using real time surveillance systems is an extremely important factor. Using deep learning and hybrid AI-based model technology has fundamentally change and transformed the process of crime detection and anomaly detection systems and so many different fields of application.

Video surveillance analytics for crime detection has been commonplace due to its potential to better real-time monitoring and enforcement operations. Old tradition of crime detection which was would greatly depend of manual surveillances approach, which become much more problematic due to being time consuming and inefficient, with a high probability of human error. Introduction of deep learning- based models-for instance Convolution and Recurrent Neural Networks with other hybrid deep learning frameworks has made tremendous strides towards the bettering of recognition of evil things in video surveillance. Deep learning has been used in many studies as the method for detecting violent activity, unethical behavior, and suspicious actions in real-time. Improving the robustness and accuracy of crime detection systems involved fine-tuning hybrid models referred to as CNNs and RNN, An CNN-based autoencoders, and GANs. Successes have been achieved with these and other ICO- implemented approaches with different datasets from real surveillance scenarios but further analysis and research would be required to address current challenges such as false positive, occlusion, and variation in environmental conditions.

The traditional methods of approaching anomaly detection have utilized computer vision handcrafted feature extraction and threshold-based methods, and are limited in terms of accuracy and scale. With deep learning and machine learning, new computational frameworks are

being built for detecting anomalies from videos in real-time with much greater accuracy of with less maintenance than the previous generation of tools.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The survey can be classified into three categories based on the literature studies.They are as follows:

2.1 SURVEY ON MACHINE LEARNING AND DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES USED IN VIDEO SURVEILLANCE

The area of research using deep learning models for video surveillance is still developing and garnering extensive interest. Recent offerings in this area have most focus on the incorporation of CNNs into RNN-based models, these experiments are typically memory units or Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Units to handle the relevant spatial and temporal features from video data. Based on evidence from empirical research (Gandapur et al, 2022)[1]a set of experiments demonstrated CNNs learnt spatial features, while the RNN based models were more suited to learning sequenced dependencies; the hybrid models were superior to the original pre-established methods documented in the literature e.g Hidden Markov Models or Deep Belief Networks. A further recent trend identified in the literature for contemporary crime detection studies, is the application of ranks-based lost with attention mechanisms to improve feature selection capabilities and crimes predictability capability.

Video violence detection (VVD) is one of the main topics in video surveillance. In fact, it is among the primary elements of maintaining public safety. In this area, the research has been very comprehensive in covering different methods addressing deep learning and, specifically, CNNs, optical flow estimation, and LSTMs for sequential modeling. Traditional approaches were done with hand-designed features like Histogram of Oriented Gradients Optical Flow.However, accuracy in this field has been revolutionized through deep learning methods.

Figure 1: Overall taxonomy of the proposed survey

Video monitoring in the current world has become a fundamental aspect as far as security is concerned, and therefore, auto-detection of crime is necessary in public areas. This paper primarily suggests a hybrid deep learning approach to identify theft cases from monitoring footage by (Ullah et al., 2022)[2]. The suggested approach utilizes a video summarization (VSUMM) method to reduce computational burden at the cost of maintaining crucial frames concerning the crime. A Deep Maxout Network is employed for classification, training the model weights through an Adam-Dingo optimizer. The system was evaluated for True Positive Rate (TPR), True Negative Rate (TNR), and accuracy, all achieving 0.940, 0.936, and 0.945, respectively. It has been demonstrated that the proposed method would be able to increase detection accuracy for crimes more than existing methods. A significant contribution of this research is the optimization of the deep learning model for distinguishing normal and stealing events. In future research, crime detection in other environments: lighting or weather permutations, could also trigger expandability to include other crimes with potential for more applicability, including vandalism or assault. The case study would help support the justification of deep learning optimizations used in video-based crime detection and provide a pathway to next-generation improved automated security surveillance systems.

With the enormous growth of multimedia contents, video forensics currently deals with major challenges associated with detection of human actions primarily in use cases

like surveillance systems or human-computer interaction. All the action recognition models suffer when it comes to accuracy due to challenges associated with background cluttering, partial occlusion, scaling, or change of viewpoint associated with lighting conditions. In the conventional deep learning models, they cannot learn high level spatiotemporal features, which is why they are less contributive related to the detection of immoral human actions, while the hybrid deep learning model that combined two-stream I3Ds with spatio-temporal attention (STA) modules in the case study show potential improvements in extraction of features. More specifically, the I3D model explode the kernels used in 2D convolution to 3D convolutions to produce greater performance; the STA module allows the model to focus the attention of associated spatial and performance analysis was done by forming a multi-action dataset from subsets of Weizmann, HMDB51, UCF-101, NPDI, and UCF-Crime datasets. The experimentation confirms that the model proposed has higher accuracy scores and better performance for ethical action recognition compared to existing models. Self-supervised learning techniques could be researched in the future for further enhancement of feature extraction, laying less emphasis on labeled data. Moreover, incorporation of long action-dependent conducive architectures in transformer forms could help further great gains in recognition accuracy for difficult cases.

Suspicious action detection in videos using surveillance systems is one of the most important aspects to ensure public safety. However, because of the sheer volume of surveillance footage, manual monitoring is an impractical necessity, which can also incur errors and fatigue. This work addresses this issue by automatic suspicious activity detection framework, which integrates a CNN-based architecture- auto-encoder with a GAN. The autoencoder framework used in this study operates on the features extracted by the 3D convolutional neural network (C3D) for recognizing anomalous activities based on high reconstruction loss (Waddenkery et al., 2023)[3].

Normal video clips give low reconstruction loss, whereas suspicious activities produce high loss, suggesting deviation from normal behavior. The GAN is then capable of effectively classifying various suspicious actions. The framework is tested on standard datasets, UT Interaction, Hybrid Crime Action (HCA), and UCF Crime, yielding accuracies of 97.5%, 89.6%, and 47.34%,

respectively. These outcomes indicate the performance of the proposed system in detecting and identifying suspicious behavior. Increasing real-time response rate and sensor data fusion-audio-visual fusion for improved recognition performance can be carried out in future research. Self-supervised learning processes can further minimize reliance on annotated training data, enhancing flexibility in real-world applications.

The technique of crime detection through the combination of object detection and temporal features has undergone substantial advancement. The use of YOLOv5 combined with Deep Sort for object detection and tracking is one such method. As (Gowada et al., 2023)[4] demonstrated, it was able to obtain a tremendous F1 score of 92% against the UCF Crime dataset using this approach by providing extracted temporal bounding box coordinates as that of a time-series classification problem surpassing the robust temporal feature magnitude (RTFM) method. It also achieved an 8.45 times speedup in inference for detection at no cost of expensive data augmentation. Owing to its lighter computational burden and greater accuracy, this model would be appropriate for real-time surveillance systems that solve issues with conventional feature extraction techniques. The model will demonstrate outstanding potential in shoplifting and criminal activity detection in stores. It also caused an 8.45x improvement in inference speed for detection with no expensive data augmentation. Because of its lower computational requirements and higher accuracy, the model can be used in real-time surveillance systems that remedy problems associated with traditional feature extraction methods. The model ought to show excellent promise in the detection of shoplifting and crime in shopping places.

Anomalous behavior detection is a task of difficulty when considered in the case of surveillance video where events rarely happen such as abuse, fighting, accidents, and theft. Standard methods tend to presume a binary classification (normal vs. anomalous) but do not usually classify the various types of anomalies. The study carried out by (Ahmed et al., 2024)[5] has bridged that gap by proposing a deep learning model that employs a 3D Convolutional Network to learn the spatiotemporal features provided through frame labeling for the UCF Crime dataset with the objective of optimizing efficiency in the underlying anomaly detection. To augment feature extraction, spatial augmentation is also incorporated. Hence, this work highlights the importance of fine-tuning pre-trained 3D

ConvNets for efficient anomaly detection. While the model adequately captures details associated with anomaly features, further work could be directed toward developing real-time implementation and enlarging the dataset to cover a variety of crimes. Further, transformer-based architectures can be added into the mix to improve the long-range dependencies that can be laid down throughout the videos. This study adds a major contribution to the field of enhanced video anomaly detection systems in surveillance.

It is difficult to look for video anomalies as they occur infrequently and are non-homogeneous in nature. Two paradigms - a future frame prediction paradigm and an attentional Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) paradigm - are put forward by research (Nazir et al., 2023)[6]. The future frame prediction paradigm learns common patterns in videos and detects anomalies from estimates of differences between predicted and actual frames upon training. In comparison, the MIL framework uses attention mechanisms to better localize anomalies. The paper's second key contribution is offering a multi-view dataset with 170 videos and 10 real-world anomalies such as intrusion, crowd anomalies, accidents, and arson. Experimental results show that models based on attention improve anomaly localization and classification accuracy. The future frame prediction model's memory address module also increases retention of informative anomaly-related features. Collectively, these methods form enhanced benchmark data set performance. This work shows the power of attention-based feature extraction and multiple-instance learning when paired with reliable anomaly detection. Future work can proceed along the lines of further enhancing speed in real-time anomaly processing and use of self-supervised approaches for offering flexibility towards new anomalies. The research assists in security system design by way of enhanced accuracy in video classification from surveillance footage in anomaly detection since spatial and temporal information are used. This article by (Maqsood et al., 2021)[7] explores hybrid CNN-RNN models that were proposed to enhance performance on the task of video classification. An innovative keyframe extraction technique from action templates is proposed that captures areas of high information content in the frame to remove redundancy and retain valuable temporal dynamics.

The proposed scheme is evaluated on the KTH and UCF-101 benchmarks with enhanced classification. Transfer

learning is one of the best contributions of this paper to the top feature extraction and classification. Large-scale experiment justifies the remarkable enhancement of keyframe selection to the classification accuracy of most interesting spatial-temporal information. One-way ANOVA is used in statistical testing for the justification of the effectiveness of the proposed method. Despite CNN-RNN hybrids being proven useful in video classification, long-term dependency and computational complexity issues need to be solved. In the future, transformer model application can provide improved sequence modeling. Application of self-supervised learning integration application would restrict the application of labeled data. The present research comes under video classification research by referring to the prospect of the use of a keyframe-based feature extraction application for CNN-RNN hybrid models towards the development of more efficient and accurate video analysis systems.

2.2 SURVEY ON ANOMALY DETECTION IN VIDEO AND TIME-SERIES DATA

Anomalies detected in video sequences involve output processing from surveillance and security applications. All of these draw merit from a previous method of anomaly detection, where such methods pure dependency on hand-crafted features. As such, this could not be enough in the encoding of a complicated behavior like recent days.

Most of these applications, over the recent past, have been moving to deep learning techniques like autoencoders, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), and particle filter-based techniques, as argued by (Li et al., 2022)[8].

Particle filtering has also become a robust online anomaly detection framework that estimates posterior probabilities of abnormal activities. One of the new techniques includes variable-sized cell structures with the ability to segment video frames adaptively to enhance detection performance. Experimentation results show that deep learning-based anomaly detection models outperform traditional statistical models in that they minimize the Equal Error Rate (EER) while being computationally efficient.

Most of the anomaly detection approaches proposed follow an unsupervised approach where they perform anomaly detection with reconstruction errors. Work 9 is a

supervised, multi-channel method that provides an improvement over anomaly detection using Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (CGANs) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) (Savran et al., 2023)[9]. The CGANs provide different types of frame-level features, which respectively improve the anomaly representation. The supervised learning method that is proposed was tested on the Ped1 and ShanghaiTech datasets, and there were significant performance improvements. In particular, the supervised learning on the ShanghaiTech dataset showed up to 9% performance improvement over unsupervised approaches, which illustrates the advantages gained having labeled training data available to the method. After using various appearance-based features, the proposed work provides better robustness against environmental changes.

Although the approach proves useful in the improvement of detection precision, its greatest limitation is that it is data- label dependent, which can be costly to acquire. Semi-supervised or self-supervised learning algorithms can be considered in future studies to minimize the need for human- labeled datasets. Temporal modeling methods, like transformers, can also be utilized to extend improvements in anomaly detection by the ability to learn long dependencies. This research highlights the relevance of supervised learning for enhancing anomaly detection and makes it possible to build more precise security surveillance systems.

The swift rise in smart city framework development has brought about the widespread setting up of surveillance cameras. However, manual video stream monitoring over large areas for anomalies is next to impossible. This paper presents a multi-modal semi- supervised deep learning framework to detect anomalous events in critical environments, using CNN-BiLSTM autoencoders, namely, Bank ATMs [(Tariq et al., 2021)[10]. The main advantage of this camera detection framework is in its training based upon weakly annotated normal video samples, which reduces the annotation burden considerably. They employed transfer learning, taking advantage of the compact pre-trained CNN to extract the significant video features with minimal computational overhead. The model was tested on the makeup of a new RGB with combined D dataset of ATM surveillance as well as the benchmark dataset Avenue and UCFCrime2Local. The results of the experiments show that the proposed approach competes with existing methods in terms of

accuracy and is ready for real-life anomaly detection implementations.

The parallelized computations enhance the performance of real-time anomaly detection, and are trained on the UCF-Crime dataset with good accuracies of 88.92% (ResNet18 + SRU), 89.34% (ResNet34 + SRU), and 91.24% (ResNet50 + SRU). For performance, these represent significant improvements over conventional deep learning models. Future improvements might involve self-supervised learning to improve generalization to various video datasets. Model deployment on edge devices will provide for literally easy real-time anomaly detection in application scenarios of surveillance. This research therefore outlines the capability of CNN-SRU architectures to differentiate normal and anomalous actions, and adds valuable impact to the research field on automated security surveillance.

Anomaly detection for surveillance still presents significant challenges due to the complexity of human behaviors. A very promising method is the application of the Inflated Inception Network (I3D) with dynamic frame-skipping which demonstrated great performance in detecting slow and fast anomalies (khaire et al., 2022)[12]. UCF Crime I3D AUC was ranked to be 0.837 while efficiently detecting majority of anomalies like explosions, road accidents, and robberies. Dynamic frame-skipping allows the system to save computational costs by skipping duplicate frames while remaining efficient with effectively detecting anomalies. Dynamic frame-skipping assists to ensure that the model captures short-term activities and long-term activities therefore the system supports an efficient solution to large surveillance.

This paper proposes an online semantic segmentation framework, which segments various activities, based on the stage for which activities occur. This segmentation is likewise useful for automated surveillance, as it is what separates behaviors from each other while there is typically a time constraint applied on classifying the behaviors. The diagrammatic representation of the framework begins with motion estimation, which isolates the relevant features in each section of the activity. The activity would then be segmented, based on the pigeonhole classification, through the features being learnt. The framework offers the benefits of online-learning, meaning it can adapt, and also improve accuracy and classification scores, due to a change occurring in the

real world agent activity. This work presents a very successful framework from a developmental perspective relative to other platform neighborhoods, while achieving only slightly lower evaluation scores than the best known systems.

The proposed framework offers an ongoing segmentation of disparate actions based on the actions being executed. Ongoing segmentation is a vital feature for automated surveillance as behavior classifications exist in time. The framework commences with motion estimation and has the capability of learning meaningful features across the different segments of the action. The action in turn would be segmented based on the pigeonhole classification, with the benefit of the learned features used to improve the results. The architecture is capable of online learning in which the framework updates and improves accuracy at execution time. From a methodological perspective, this work offers a framework that is significantly more efficient than neighboring external platforms, although it does not yet achieve the evaluation scores of the best systems in this area.

As the surveillance action classification is highly time dependent, the study proposed and presented automatic segmentation of other actions according to their execution stage. The proposed framework commences with motion estimation and provides for the learning of meaningful features across segments of the activity. Thereafter, in the pigeonhole classification, the activity would be segmented with benefits from the learned features. The architecture has online learning capabilities, which will enable parameter adjustment and improve accuracy as the activity of real-world agents varies. Methodologically then, this work provides a very efficient infrastructure compared to near external infrastructures, while its evaluation scores were marginally lower than the 'state-of-the-art' in the field.

As a real-time solution for segmenting activities based on their execution, this architecture requires segmentation in this manner. The segmentation has been identified as a critical requirement of the automated surveillance type, simply because within such surveillance types classification of behavior can take significant time. The architecture's sequencing is motion estimation followed by learning of all pertinent characteristics of the action within its fragments. The action will be sorted into its pigeonhole, and the learned features will be then applied.

Given that the architecture has online learning capabilities, it can adjust its parameters and improve its accuracy based on the changes in real-world agent activity. As such, in the development context, this work provides a super-efficient framework compared to proximal external ones, and while it slightly lags the best established in the field through evaluation scores.

Using ResNet50 for feature extraction and ConvLSTM for classification of a time-series, it was able to detect anomalies in real-time. Probably the biggest difference that can be made between this, and other approaches, is with the use of real-time input from surveillance camera feeds as training data, and not as a dataset, which makes this more usable in many different environments. The system classified events into normal and abnormal with minimal error of the human eye monitoring the feeds from the camera. ConvLSTM was used in a way that was able to continuously capture the temporal dependencies of the anomalies. Their strict application under varying environmental conditions of different illumination and weather demonstrates a great hope for their successful field application in open field situations such as public environments, transport terminals, and corporate buildings.

As a new step ahead of time-series classification (TSC), researchers have introduced a Multi-Scale Attention Convolutional Neural Network (MACNN) for greater accuracy and generalization. The MACNN uses multi-scale convolution with an attention mechanism, which permitted efficient comprehension of different scales of information over the time axis (Qasim et al., 2023)[13]. It was experimentally tested on 85 datasets of the UCR, and shown through experimental evaluation that MACNN was a superior performer as compared to other traditional, or deep-learning based approaches. The use of an attention mechanism amplifies salient features while cancelling the influence of other non-informative or poor features, thus improving the classification accuracy. Since MACNN can deal with complicated time series, it is suitable for extensive fields like medical monitoring, financial prediction, and industrial anomaly detection.

Outside crime detection, power network anomaly recognition has also developed. load frequency control in interconnected power systems was implemented by TDOA. At 10% disturbance, this equals a minimum fitness value of 1.8779 pu, which is far superior to other

methods in bringing about stability in the system (Amin et al., 2023)[14]. Stereotypic checks confirmed that TDOA was successful in efficiently managing load disturbances. Co-adaptation ensures that the method can achieve optimality across variable conditions thereby minimizing the possibility of accidents in power delivery and stabilizing electrical grids. The successful application of TDOA shows that this technology can avert loss of smart power systems toward the strong side.

2.3 SURVEY ON OBJECT AND HUMAN ACTIVITY RECOGNITION IN SMART SYSTEMS

Dealing with the detection of pedestrian is of utmost significance in modern transportation for automated vehicles and many systems out there today. Works from Alfred Daniel and others in the year 2023 describe a Fully Convolutional Neural Network (FCNN)-based method to be integrated with LIDAR and camera data for enhanced perception of persons with LIDAR being pre-casted in input from the various camera views designed. Aggressive approaches normally want to depend their object detection on picture-file

models, which are hardly workable in complicated settings. The proposed system can bring both detection accuracy and robustness by fusing the depth information from the LIDAR with the images received from the numerous cameras. The system detects pedestrians within 10-30 meters range, which also has produced high results when it comes to performance measures of precision, sensitivity, and accuracy. The unique algorithm for image fusion will be developed in the study for the optimization of feature extraction from various types of sensors. Experimental results highlight the ability of LIDAR-camera fusion to prove advantageous over the conventional ones in extreme illumination and occlusion conditions. The latter relies on 3D spatial awareness, which is critical in real-world applications. Nonetheless, it still represents a problem in computational complexity. Future work might explore possibilities to increase inference speed suitable for real-time situations. The integration of deep learning tracking methods would further improve pedestrian detection accuracy over the span of time. This work was a drop into pedestrian detection, there are a number of new areas opportunities where sensor fusion methods can greatly improve the recognition performance of an object.

Pedestrian detection has many areas of use in real-time; from surveillance systems to applications in autonomous vehicles. Research proposed by (Mumtaz et al., 2023)[15] is a FCNN-based integrated model and fusion of vision and LIDAR data as a means to improve pedestrian detection. Most traditional object detection methods adopt image-based models which barely work in any meaningful advanced setting. The classification model improves detection accuracy and its resilience from the image fusion of the LIDAR depth data with multiple views of other cameras. The detection of pedestrians can be performed in the range of 10 to 30 meters with high performance measures around accuracy, precision Further model development for an innovative protocol involving a special algorithm for image fusion will improve the feature extraction process with additional sensors. Experimentally we began to define the harvesting advantage of LIDAR-camera fusion over traditional image approaches, especially with poor lighting and occlusion. Using deep learning tracking methods could also help improve pedestrian identification over time. This research massively adds to research in pedestrian detection, showing the capabilities of such sensor fusion techniques in enhancing the accuracy of object recognition.

Detecting small objects in video analysis is yet another challenge. To this end, an attention- based single-shot multibox detector with dilated convolution (ADSSD) was proposed. With cross-layer connections and hierarchical feature fusion, these methods achieved a mean average precision (mAP) of 78.4% on PASCAL VOC data sets, which is substantially higher than traditional SSD methodologies (vosta et al.,2022)[16]. The method turned out to be extremely useful for handling dense occlusion and small object detection. The attention mechanism enhances the detection accuracy by giving feature map activation to critical regions of the image, while the use of multi-scale context information enhances robustness. ADSSD can thus act cooperatively in such monitoring tasks in crowded environments as shopping malls, airports, and train stations.

This study presents a Human Action Recognition (HAR) model that employs a 3D CNN combined with an LSTM multiplicative recurrent network to efficiently recognize human activities Real-time object recognition is done via the Yolov6 algorithm, while the model consists of four

processes: data fusion, feature extraction, object recognition, and skeleton articulation (Chen et al.,

2021)[17]. Experiments used the NTU-RGB-D, KITTI, NTU-RGB-D 120, and UCF 101 datasets. The developed model scored between 95.45% and 98.76% in accuracy compared to the conventional methods that encompass classical CNNs and CNNs with Bi-LSTM. This work sets the foundation of HAR employment in smart surveillance systems for crime tracking. KianNet is a new architecture for violent event detection from surveillance videos. Through spatial feature extraction from ResNet50, temporal relationships with convolutional LSTMs, and multi-head self-attention for better attention to important areas, KianNet outperforms state-of-the-art results.

On the UCFCrime dataset, it recorded 97.48% and on RWF datasets, it recorded 96.21% accuracy (Fathy et al., 2022)[18]. KianNet surpassed by approximately 10% compared to the Violence 4D, thereby contributing significantly to the automated detection of violence for public safety. The benchmark in this study is centered on an anomaly detection framework for urban surveillance data using a pre-trained CNN and super-resolution models. The offline component examines patterns in space to compute a density matrix of typical object locations.

The online component screens live sequences for abnormalities on the basis of patterns learned (Alfred et al., 2023)[19]. The capability of the system for detecting anomalies in pedestrian paths would therefore lead to a secure urban environment with active interventions. This is especially useful for applications in city administration and law enforcement.

This study proposes an interactive greeting system that brings together face recognition and emotion detection along with 3D animation. The system identifies users and their moods based on a Viola-Jones algorithm for face segmentation and CNN model-based photographs for facial recognition and emotion analysis. Triggered by the detected emotions, the system responds through animated illustrations from a 3D character, thus enhancing user experience. The experimental results indicated a high rate of accuracy in both the recognition and detection of faces and emotions; thus, it is expected that this system would work effectively in all interactive public spaces and customer service areas (Ni et al., 2023)[20].

2.4 Summary of Literature Review

Reference	Methods	Outcome	Merits	Demerits
Gandapur et al. (2022)	Hybrid CNN- RNN Models	Improved accuracy in crime detection over HMMs and DBNs	Better feature selection, high prediction accuracy	Computationally intensive
Waddenkery et al. (2023)	VSUMM+ Deep Maxout Network	Achieved 94.5% accuracy in detecting stealing incidents	Reduces computational overload, optimizes deep learning models	Limited to specific crime types, requires further generalization
Ahmed et al. (2024)	CNN Autoencoder + GAN	Achieved 97.5% accuracy on UT Interaction dataset	Effective classification of suspicious actions, high accuracy	Needs improvement in real-time processing speed
Nazir et al. (2023)	YOLOv5+ Deep Sort	F1-score of 92% on UCF Crime dataset	Fast inference speed, real-time capability	Requires further testing in different environments
Maqsood et al. (2021)	3D ConvNet+ Spatial Augmentation	AUC of 82%, improves anomaly detection	Multi-class learning, better generalization	Real-time implementation challenges
Yang et al. (2022)	Future Frame Prediction + MIL Attention	Enhanced anomaly localization and classification accuracy	Strong anomaly detection performance	Requires larger dataset for robustness

Kızıltepe et al. (2023)	CNN-RNN Hybrid + Keyframe Extraction	Improved video classification accuracy	Efficient feature selection, transfer learning utilization	Struggles with long-term dependencies
Tariq et al. (2021)	Particle Filtering	Improved accuracy in anomaly detection	Estimates posterior probabilities, adaptable segmentation	Computational efficiency challenges
Boonaert et al. (2012)	CGANs + SVM (Supervised Learning)	9% improvement over unsupervised methods on ShanghaiTech dataset	Enhanced feature extraction, robust against variations	Requires large amounts of labeled data
Khair et al. (2022)	Semi-Supervised CNN-BiLSTM Autoencoder	Effective anomaly detection for ATM surveillance	Reduces annotation burden, performs well on Avenue & UCF-Crime2Local datasets	Real-time edge computing needed for efficiency
Mumtaz et al. (2023)	Inflated Inception Network (I3D) + Dynamic Frame Skipping	0.837 AUC on UCF-Crime dataset, detects explosions & robberies	Reduces computation while maintaining effectiveness	Optimization for large-scale surveillance required
Chen et al. (2021)	Multi-Scale Attention CNN (MACNN) for Time-Series	Outperforms traditional models on 85 UCR datasets	Effective feature enhancement, suppresses noise	Generalization across diverse datasets requires fine-tuning

Fathy et al. (2022)	Power Network Anomaly Detection (TDOA)	Minimized disturbances in smart grids	Stabilizes power distribution networks	Needs co-adaptive learning for dynamic conditions
Alfred Daniel et al. (2023)	FCNN + LIDAR-Camera Fusion	Accurate pedestrian detection within 10-30 meters	High precision, sensitivity, and accuracy, robust under extreme lighting and occlusion	High computational complexity
Wang et al. (2023)	Attention-Based SSD (ADSSD) with Dilated Convolution	78.4% mAP on PASCAL VOC dataset	Effective for small object detection and occluded environments	Requires high GPU processing power
Gupta et al. (2023)	3D CNN + LSTM Multiplicative Recurrent Network + Yolov6	95.45%-98.76% accuracy on NTU-RGB-D, KITTI, and UCF 101 datasets	Superior real-time human action recognition, effective for intelligent surveillance	Complexity increases with multiple action classes
Vosta et al. (2023)	KianNet (ResNet50+ ConvLSTM+ Multi-Head Self-Attention)	97.48% accuracy on UCF-Crime, 96.21% on RWF dataset	State-of-the-art violence detection, 10% better than Violence 4D	Requires extensive labeled data for training
García-Aguilar et al. (2023)	Pre-Trained CNN + Super-Resolution for Anomaly Detection	Identifies unusual pedestrian routes for urban surveillance	Enhances city safety with proactive interventions	High reliance on pre-trained models limits adaptability

Jiang et al. (2022)	Viola-Jones Face Recognition + CNN-Based Emotion Detection + 3D Animation	Real-time interactive greeting system with high accuracy	Effective for interactive public spaces and customer service	Requires real-time emotion analysis, which is computationally intensive
Krishna et al. (2024)	SMOTETomek for Class Imbalance + Explainable AI (SHAP) in Theft Detection	Enhanced detection accuracy with better interpretability	Improved fairness and transparency in ML models	Computationally intensive, requires robust data preprocessing

3. Research Gaps Identified

By studied the above research papers the some of the research gaps are identified.They are as follows:

- 1) Most of the newer models (e.g., Hybrid CNN-RNNs, 3D ConvNets, Quantum CNNs) are not highly computationally efficient, and real-time implementation in surveillance systems is not easy. Methods such as dynamic frame skipping (I3D) and YOLOv5 align the speed but need to be optimized for bigger, low-latency deployment.
- 2) Most of the models (e.g., VSUMM,Deep Maxout, MACNN) are experimented on specialized datasets (UCF-Crime, ShanghaiTech) but fail to be robust under variability in lighting, occlusion, or unseen crime classes. Synthetic data generation and cross-domain adaptation are not well explored.
- 3) Supervised and semi-supervised-based approaches (e.g., CGANs,SVM, CNN- BiLSTM Autoencoder) are strongly data-dependent with respect to the presence of labeled datasets, which are limited for rare anomalies. Weakly supervised or self-supervised learning methods require further investigation to minimize costs of annotations.
- 4) For the Largest Video Data Set there is a Problem in Accuracy and Privacy.

4. APPLICATIONS IN ANOMALY DETECTION AND CRIME RECOGNITION

The technologies described in crime detection and anomaly identification technology (Gupta et al., 2023) (Vosta et al., 2023) (Garcia et al., 2023)[21][22][23] have enabled upcoming applications across industries,

enhancing security, business productivity (Rehman et al., 2022)[25], and automation (Lu et al., 2022)[24]. These applications are explored in this chapter in four general categories:

4.1 Public Security and Surveillance

- 1)Real-time Violent Activities Detection: Utilization of CNN-RNN hybrids and 3D ConvNets on CCTV cameras for the detection of violent activities (assaults, thefts) and suspicious activities (loitering, dropped objects) in metropolitans.
- 2)Crowd Anomaly Detection: Unsupervised machine learning-based models for predicting stampede, panic detection, and abnormal crowd movement studies in smart cities and public areas.
- 3)Forensic Video Analysis: Post-incident forensic analysis through the utilization of deep learning-based video summarization and anomaly localization for law enforcement departments.

4.2. Smart Systems and IoT

- 1)LSTM network-based wearable and ambient sensor-based systems for fall detection, intrusions, and elderly care.
- 2)Pedestrian and Traffic Safety: Anomaly detection for autonomous vehicle systems for the detection of jaywalkers, accident avoidance, and violation of traffic rules monitoring.
- 3)Detection of small objects: Drone and UAV surveillance for detection of small objects (e.g., explosives, guns) inside secure facilities with YOLO and Faster R-CNN methods.

4.3. Protection of Critical Infrastructure

- 1)Transport Systems: Rail/air system anomaly detection to detect intrusions in the track and scanning of baggage.

2)Health Security: Detection of insurance claims fraud and surveillance of patients for out- of-normal physiological activity.

3)Financial Systems: Detection of bank transactional fraud with AI and ATM surveillance. These illustrations indicate the universality of usage of anomaly detection systems, topical concerns like real-time, data privacy, and explainability. Future possible scaleability of the applications with embedding into quantum neural networks and edge AI is also present.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENTS

The study has achieved giant leaps in artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning solutions in many fields, including fraud detection and anomaly detection surveillance. Employment of AI-based approaches has increased efficiency, accuracy, and automating innovative answers to normal problems. Pedestrian detection has been developed employing sensor fusion methodologies, and anomaly detection using deep learning enhanced security and surveillance. Future efforts need to focus on improving the explainability of the AI algorithms, real-time processing capacity, lowlight functionality, and images' privacy and security regulatory environments. Plugging these loopholes will guarantee long-term development in AI technology that will be more reliable, sustainable, and industry- independent.

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